

Biamperometric Determination of Alkaline Earth Metals in Low Concentration Range

HARI PRASAD SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221005

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VARIOUS methods¹⁻¹⁵ have been used in the estimation of alkaline earth metals. Of all the methods reported in literature¹⁻¹⁵ amperometric titration has distinct advantage over the others in respect of time involved in the estimation and its applicability at low concentrations. Spectrophotometric technique has a disadvantage because it can be used only in the UV region. Ringbom and Wilkman¹⁶ estimated calcium and barium amperometrically with flouride ion at the dropping mercury electrode using trivalent iron as indicator. Faber¹⁷, Mann *et al*¹⁸ used EDTA method to determine strontium and barium using Eriochrome Black T as indicator. Malat and coworkers¹⁹ determined magnesium with EDTA using Pyrocatechol Violet as indicator. Sympson²⁰ developed an amperometric method for the titrations of calcium with EDTA. Estimation of alkaline earth metals using other methods are also reported in the literature¹⁻¹⁵.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to develop a biamperometric technique using two platinum electrodes at constant voltage for a rapid determination of alkaline earth metals at low concentrations.

Experimental

Alkaline earths salts used were of B. D. H., AR or Merck's extrapure quality. Stock solutions were prepared using conductivity water. Solutions of alkaline earth metals were standardized gravimetrically²¹ and further verified by titrating with standard EDTA solution using various indicators²¹. EDTA solutions used for titration was obtained by appropriate dilution of a strong stock solution. EDTA solution was standardized using standard method²¹.

Titrations were carried out, apparatus similar to Stone and Scholten²², platinum electrodes (of cross section 0.5 cm²) were used with a modified circuit. A constant E. M. F. of 0.9 volts in the case of magnesium and 1.0 volts in the case of other alkaline earth metals were applied from a battery. The titration mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer and the current was measured with a sensitive galvanometer.

20 ml of the test solution was placed in the titration cell fitted with a rubber stopper having holes for the burette, electrodes, nitrogen inlet and outlet, a stream of nitrogen was passed for about 5 min. pH of the solution was adjusted using monochloro acetate buffer. Standard EDTA solution was added from a 2.0 ml semimicroburette and the current through the cell was measured. Readings were taken at uniform intervals

Fig. 1—Determination of 0.3533 mg. barium present in solution

usually 30 sec. after each addition of titrants. End points were determined graphically by plotting current against volume of the titrant added. The end points were quite reproducible. A typical titration curve is shown in Figure 1. For every sample under investigation six iterated determinations were made. Results obtained are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ALKALINE EARTH METALS

S. No.	Amount of alkaline earth metals in mg		Experimental error%	
	Taken	Estimated in this work	Average	Maximum
		(magnesium)		
1	0.4862	0.4847	-0.28	-1.25
2	0.2431	0.2431	-0.57	-1.50
3	0.3647	0.3625	-0.18	-1.00
4	0.1216	0.1218	+0.87	+2.00
		(Calcium)		
5	0.4008	0.4012	+0.53	+1.50
6	0.3006	0.3015	+0.45	+1.75
7	0.2004	0.2000	-0.73	-2.0
8	0.1503	0.1500	-0.54	-1.65
		(Strontium)		
9	0.8762	0.8830	+0.84	+2.5
10	0.2190	0.2176	-0.66	-2.0
11	0.2190	0.2190	+0.0	+1.01
12	0.1095	0.1089	-0.57	-1.75
		(Barium)		
13	1.3734	1.3712	+0.37	+1.5
14	0.6867	0.6852	+0.25	+1.3
15	0.5149	0.5131	-0.33	-1.85
16	0.3533	0.3433	-0.16	-1.0

Results and Discussion

The method described is based on electro-oxidation of free EDTA on a platinum anode in the pH range of

1.5 to 2.0 for magnesium and 2.5 to 3.0 for the rest of the alkaline earth metals. On addition of EDTA solution metal chelates are formed and no electro-oxidation of EDTA occurs. If a potential of 0.9-1.0 volts is applied to two platinum electrodes the residual current is registered up to the equivalence point but the current rises abruptly due to the oxidation of EDTA after the equivalence point. The titration curve has usually the shape of reverse L type. The reaction involved in the present titration is stoichiometric and quantitative with a sharp break at 1:1 ratio between elements and EDTA ions. The results obtained were within 1.0% error.

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Studies on s-Triazinyl Aryl/Alkyl Sulphones. Part I. Preparation of 4'-(2-p-Chlorophenylsulphonyl-4-Aryl/Alkyl Amino-s-Triazin-6-yl)-Aminobenzoic Acid

M. H. GOGHARI and A. R. PARIKH

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

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P-AMINO BENZOIC acid derivatives have been found to be powerful local anaesthetic¹, important metabolite for many micro-organisms² and possess bacteriostatic property³. s-Triazine derivatives⁴⁻¹⁰ also possess therapeutic activity. With a view that more powerful therapeutic agent can be obtained, we have prepared substituted s-triazinyl aminobenzoic acid derivatives of the type I i.e., 4'-(2-p-chlorophenylsulphonyl-4-aryl/alkyl-amino-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid.

(I)

Where R=arylamino, alkylamino, etc.

The first chlorine of 2, 4, 6-trichloro-s-triazin was reacted with *p*-chlorothiophenol¹¹ at 0° leading to the formation of 2, 4-dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide. The second chlorine reacted with *p*-aminobenzoic acid at 30°-35° and the third chlorine at 80°-90° with different bases using dioxan as solvent. The product obtained was then oxidised to the corresponding sulphone.

Experimental

(a) **2, 4-Dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide**: Cyanuric chloride (9.2 g) was dissolved in acetone (25 ml) and kept at 0°. *p*-Chlorothiophenol (7.25 g) dissolved in acetone (25 ml) was gradually added with constant stirring followed by aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (25 ml, 7%). The reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour and poured in crushed ice. The product obtained was filtered and dried; yield 13.00 g (88.90%), M. P. 116°-118°.

(b) **4'-(2-*p*-Chlorophenylthio-4-chloro-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoic acid**: *p*-Aminobenzoic acid (6.85 g) dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 20%) was added to the suspension of 2, 4-Dichloro-s-triazin-6-yl-*p*-chlorophenylsulphide (14.62 g) in dioxan (50 ml) at 30°-35°. The contents were stirred for an hour with the gradual addition of an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 20%) and diluted with ice water. The solution thus obtained was acidified with concentrated